

On the abc Conjecture

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Abstract

It is shown that the abc conjecture does not hold.

1 Introduction

The abc conjecture is a conjecture proposed by Masser [1] and Oesterlé [2] in 1985 and 1988, respectively. It states that, for every $\epsilon > 0$, there exists only a finite number of triples (a, b, c) of coprime positive integers, with $a + b = c$, such that:

$$c > rad(abc)^{1+\epsilon} \quad (1)$$

where the radical of n , denoted $rad(n)$, is the product of the distinct prime factors of n .

2 Finding $c > rad(abc)^{1+\epsilon}$

Let μ be such that

$$\frac{1}{\mu} = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{1}{b} \quad (2)$$

or

$$\mu \frac{a+b}{ab} = 1 \quad (3)$$

We know that

$$a b \geq rad(a) rad(b) \quad (4)$$

so

$$\mu \frac{a+b}{rad(a)rad(b)} \geq 1 \quad (5)$$

Let τ be such that

$$\mu = \frac{\tau}{rad(c)} \quad (6)$$

Substituting (6) into (5) we have

$$\frac{\tau(a+b)}{rad(a)rad(b)rad(c)} \geq 1 \quad (7)$$

Let ν be such that

$$\frac{\tau}{rad(a)rad(b)rad(c)} = \frac{1}{(rad(a)rad(b)rad(c))^{1+\nu}} \quad (8)$$

or

$$\tau = \frac{1}{(rad(a)rad(b)rad(c))^\nu} \quad (9)$$

With (9) the equation (6) becomes

$$\mu = \frac{1}{rad(c)^{1+\nu} (rad(b)rad(b))^\nu} \quad (10)$$

Substituting (10) into (5) we found

$$\frac{c}{\left(\text{rad}(a)\text{rad}(b)\text{rad}(c)\right)^{1+\nu}} \geq 1 \quad (11)$$

Let us assume

$$\nu > 0 \quad (12)$$

Since ν is a positive number we have from (9)

$$0 < \tau < 1 \quad (13)$$

and from (8)

$$0 < \mu \times \text{rad}(c) < 1 \quad (14)$$

Substituting μ from (4) into (14) we found

$$0 < \frac{ab}{a+b} \text{rad}(c) < 1 \quad (15)$$

or

$$0 < \frac{\text{rad}(abc)}{c} < 1 \quad (16)$$

From (11) and (16) we obtain

$$\frac{c}{\left(\text{rad}(a)\text{rad}(b)\text{rad}(c)\right)^{1+\nu}} > \frac{\text{rad}(abc)}{c} \quad (17)$$

or

$$c > \text{rad}(abc)^{1+\frac{\nu}{2}} \quad (18)$$

Let us denote $\frac{\nu}{2}$ by ϵ and (18) becomes equal to (1). From (16) we found

$$c > \text{rad}(abc) \quad (19)$$

and from (18), (19) and using ϵ we have

$$c > \text{rad}(abc)^{1+\epsilon} > \text{rad}(abc) \quad (20)$$

We obtained (20) without any indication that the abc conjecture is true. Now we try to find a counterexample.

3 The proof

Let a , b and c be equal to

$$a = 2^2 \quad (21)$$

$$b = 3^n - 2^2 \quad (22)$$

and

$$c = 3^n \quad (23)$$

where \mathcal{N} is the set of natural numbers and n belongs to the set

$$\mathcal{S} = \left\{ n \mid n \in \mathcal{N} \text{ and } n > 1 \text{ and } \frac{3^n - 2^2}{3} \text{ is not an integer} \right\} \quad (24)$$

Let us note that

$$\frac{3^n - 2^2}{3} = 3^{n-1} - \frac{4}{3} \quad (25)$$

for all natural numbers greater than 1. In this case we have

$$rad(abc) = rad(a) rad(b) rad(c) \quad (26)$$

or

$$rad(abc) = 2 rad(3^n - 2^2) 3 \quad (27)$$

Let us rewrite the right side of (27) as

$$rad(3^n - 2^2)^{1+\epsilon} \quad (28)$$

In (28) we have for each value of n a positive ϵ . The value of ϵ decreases with the increase of n .

Let d and e be equal to

$$d = 3^m - 2^2 \quad (29)$$

and

$$e = 3^m \quad (30)$$

where m belongs to the set

$$\mathcal{M} = \left\{ m \mid m \in \mathcal{S} \text{ and } \frac{3^m - 2^2}{5} \text{ is not an integer} \right\} \quad (31)$$

so a , d and e are coprimes

$$e = a + d \quad (32)$$

and

$$|\mathcal{M}| = |\mathcal{N}| \quad (33)$$

Similarly to (27) and (28) we can write

$$rad(ade) = rad(3^m - 2^2)^{1+\epsilon} \quad (34)$$

where ϵ is a function of m . Since

$$rad(abc) > rad(ade) \quad (35)$$

we have

$$rad(abc) > rad(3^m - 2^2)^{1+\epsilon} \quad (36)$$

Substituting (19) into (36) we obtain

$$c > rad(3^m - 2^2)^{1+\epsilon} \quad (37)$$

Let us notice that

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{rad(abc)}{rad(3^m - 2^2)^{1+\epsilon}} = 1 \quad (38)$$

but considering (19) we have that (37) is true for all values of m . Since the cardinality of \mathcal{M} is equal to the cardinality of the natural numbers, we can conclude that the abc conjecture is not true.

References

- [1] Masser, D. W., *Open problems*, in Chen, W. W. L. Proceedings of the Symposium on Analytic Number Theory, Imperial College, London, 1985.
- [2] Oesterlé, J., *Nouvelles approches du "théorème" de Fermat*, Séminaire Bourbaki, volume 30, p. 165-186, 1988.